

MANAGING COMPETENCIES OF THE ARALING PANLIPUNAN 7 THROUGH THE USE OF MOBILE-ASSISTED LEARNING MATERIALS

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Managing Competencies of the Araling Panlipunan 7 Through the Use of Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop and utilize Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials for Araling Panlipunan Grade 7 students at San Jose National High School, District II-A, Division Office of Antipolo City during the School Year 2023-2024. The researcher employed experimental research. Specifically, one-group pre and post-test designs. Validated test questionnaires by experts served as the primary data gathering instrument. Based on the identified least competencies were the basis for developing a mobile-assisted learning material. In addition, the material that could be developed was Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials with Kotobee Apps downloaded from the Play Store, the most recent e-book reading software accessible on the Software Store. As the score revealed from the data, it can be noted that during the pretest most of the students acquired scores of 16-20 on their test which is defined as a low mastery level since the competencies have not been taught by the teacher and the mobile-assisted have not been used. It can be noted that teaching using mobile-assisted learning materials has a better impact on student performance as most of the students acquired scores of 21-25 in their tests it can be inferred that there is an increase in their scores after they are exposed to the developed material which is the mobile-assisted learning materials. Enhancements may be considered in the developed mobile-assisted learning materials based on the results of test scores in the competency assessment.

Keywords: *kotobee, learning material, araling panlipunan*

Introduction

Education is one of the most important things in life, particularly, high-quality education, which includes quality teaching, instructional resources, teaching strategies, and teacher competency, all have a significant impact on student accomplishment. Students can acquire knowledge and become competitive graduates in the future by providing them with instructional materials that use advanced media and great instruction from their teachers.

At present cellphones are the most utilized medium of learning. Classes are conducted using different video conferencing applications such as Google Meet and Zoom. Instructional materials were sent to the learners by using downloadable applications such as Google Classroom, Facebook, and Messenger, allowing learners to access educational materials anywhere and anytime.

To create more complete and successful teaching practices, it is necessary to have a solid grasp of the influence of technology usage in the classroom. Instructors should know how to use a variety of smartphone applications, be proficient with computers and laptops, and be prepared to take on the challenge of instructional technology that has the potential to improve student learning and abilities.

The advent of technology brings forth sufficient resources to enhance teaching skills and learning abilities. Technology can assist teachers in an actual teaching-learning session by providing a valuable tool for an effective educational process. One of the reasons for integrating mobile-assisted learning materials in teaching is to improve, enhance, and increase the academic performance of students. Mobile devices can be considered computer devices because they use programs and systems like what is installed in personal computers and laptops.

Fortunately, solutions like Kotobee, an E-book application available in the Play Store address internet issues by functioning online and offline. Kotobee Author stands out as a professional tool for creating high-quality e-books, accepting inputs in various formats such as PDF, HTML, or Word files or allowing users to start from scratch. It could also be done in different mobile apps. This software is one of the different E-book authoring tools that are very inexpensive.

Applying technology in the teaching-learning process modernizes teachers approaches, fostering a 21st century teaching mindset focused on innovative methods and stimulating learning experiences. Mobile-assisted instructional materials, considering the widespread use of mobile devices among Filipinos, present an opportunity to overcome barriers to learning essential competencies in subjects like Araling Panlipunan, has been observed over two consecutive school years, highlighting the need for adaptive teaching strategies to address student's needs.

In San Jose National High School, a decline in students' academic performance was experienced as revealed in the two consecutive school years 44.34 MPS in 2020-2021 and 49.94 in 2021-2022 report of test results prepared by the School Testing Coordinator. The researcher handled Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan. According to the report, Grade 7 students had the lowest Mean Percentage Score (MPS) in Araling Panlipunan during the 2nd quarter based on the Quarterly Assessment test. From the results, it inferred that the students have low performance in Araling Panlipunan 7.

The researcher has been teaching Araling Panlipunan in the intermediate class for ten years, has observed student's lack of interest in

the subject due to its reliance on reading lengthy historical articles and memorizing a large number of names and dates. To combat this perception and engage students in Social Studies 7, the researcher aims to develop and utilize mobile-assisted learning materials leveraging interactive mobile applications like Kotobee. With 95% of grade 7 students at San Jose National High School having access to smartphones for educational purposes, the researcher sets to address the least mastered competencies in the subject during 2023-2024 school year.

Research Questions

Based on the result of the study, this research aimed to develop and utilize mobile-assisted learning materials for the least mastered competencies of the grade 7 students in their Araling Panlipunan subject during the school year 2023-2024 at San Jose National High School. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the three least mastered competencies of the Araling Panlipunan Grade 7 students based on the Second Quarter Periodical Test of the school year 2021-2022 and 2022-2023?
2. What material may be developed to address the least mastered competencies in Araling Panlipunan 7?
3. What are the pre-test and post-test scores based on the competency assessment in Araling Panlipunan Grade 7?
4. Is there a significant difference between the pre and post-test scores in the competency Assessment in Araling Panlipunan 7?
5. What enhancement should be considered in the developed material based on the result of test scores on the competency assessment?

Literature Review

Thamburaj (2020) asserts that mobile application-assisted learning is effective and gives teachers guidance on how to adapt their pedagogy strategy in light of the rapid advancements in technology, particularly concerning the Tamil language. The rapid advancement of mobile technology makes it possible for students to access the internet quickly and conveniently at anytime, anywhere. Mobile devices, rapid advancement and have enormous potential to impact every aspect of human existence.

In addition, as stated in the article released by SpringerLink (2021), mobile learning has gained traction with the younger generation. It encourages students to study more thoroughly, improves their ability to think critically, and produces amazing amounts of knowledge. A learning paradigm known as “mobile learning” allows students to access resources via the Internet and mobile devices anytime, anywhere.

According to Castor (2019) mobile electronics like cell phones and tablets were originally seen to be a distraction in class. While this is true, educators have gradually discovered that phones may be used as learning tools. Phones have evolved into effective teaching tools that, when utilized correctly, can increase learning outcomes. Cell phones became so popular in the late 1990s that some school administrators restricted their use in the classroom and on school grounds. Currently, the old device that educators feared has become the most popular medium of learning, particularly during this pandemic.

Likewise, as stressed by Cakmak (2019) mobile learning also referred to as m-learning was introduced as an expansion of e-learning via portable computing devices like smartphones and PDAs. Being comfortable to bring anywhere, mobile devices are a big help to bring the learning process everywhere. The researcher believed that the development of mobile-assisted learning material is an integral part of the present system of learning process where mobile devices are being utilized online or offline.

Similarly, Baring's (2022) study entitled Supporting Conceptual Comprehension of Newton's Law of Motion of Grade 8 Students through Kotobee Interactive E-Module suggests that using an e-module in the growth of science education is effective, and it presents different approaches to appropriately employ an e-module in addressing and correcting concerns and problems in the teaching and learning processes.

Furthermore, Uncad (2022), in her study entitled Intervention Material Utilizing Kotobee Application as an Aid for Modular Distance Learning for Grade 10 Mathematics, focused on the development of intervention material using the Kotobee Application as they dealt with modular distance learning. After using the Kotobee program to evaluate the prepared material, the teacher responders rated it as satisfactory, based on the results showing that the student participants performed Very Satisfactorily.

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed an experimental method of research. Specifically, one group pretest-posttest design. This design is considered the simplest form of research design where a single group is observed after some intervention/treatment that is assumed to cause a change. In this type of research design, the student participants will observe at two points: one before the treatment and one after the treatment.

There is no control or comparison group used. Changes in the outcome are presumed to be the result of the applied intervention or treatment.

Respondents

The sources of data in this study were composed of 312 student respondents from Grade Seven of San Jose National High School, Division of Antipolo City during the School Year 2023–2024. To determine the exact number of respondents Slovin's formula was used.

Instrument

The main instruments used in gathering data were the pretest and posttest. A thirty-item Grade 7 Araling Panlipunan multiple choice test was constructed with a Table of specifications which was developed by the researcher and validated by the expert and her adviser. The test was based on the three least mastered competencies used in Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials. The pretest/posttest was used to determine the effectiveness of the developed learning materials before and after the utilization of Mobile-Assisted Learning Material for Araling Panlipunan 7.

Procedure

Permission to conduct this research study will first be secured from the Schools Division Superintendent of Antipolo City as well as the School Principal of San Jose National High School before administering the study.

The researcher selected the three least mastered competencies that served as the basis for developing mobile-assisted instructional materials, following the ADDIE model.

The Kotobee program was utilized to create mobile-assisted learning materials that can be used with or without the Internet. The implementation took place at both school and home. At school, students could read text, complete assigned activities, and participate in class discussions with their teachers.

At home, students have plenty of time to navigate and study the lesson; they can view videos, read text, and participate in activities. They can simply determine if their answer is correct or incorrect. The learner-respondents were subsequently exposed to the developed mobile-assisted learning materials for three (3) weeks.

The pre-test was administered to the students who were given with one learning activity a day and discussions followed doing the MAI. After teaching using mobile-assisted learning activities, the posttest was administered. Student respondents answered the given test questionnaires. The responses of the students were gathered, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted. The obtained data were kept private for the entire duration of the study.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher observed the necessary ethics in the conduct of his study. She first informed the respondents regarding the involvement in the study and got their consent. She also explained to the respondents that their participation is voluntary and their responses to the questionnaire will be treated with utmost confidentiality and anonymity.

Results and Discussion

This portion presents the results and discussion based on the gathered data.

Three (3) Least Mastered Competencies of the Araling Panlipunan Grade 7 students

Table 1. *Three Least Mastered Competency in the Araling Panlipunan Grade 7 Students During School Year 2021-2022 and 2022-2023*

Competency	Rank
Nasusuri ang mga kalagayang legal at tradisyon ng mga kababaihan sa iba't ibang uri ng pamumuhay.	1
Nabibigyang kahulugan ang konsepto ng kabihasan at sibilisasyon at nailalahad ang mga katangian nito. Napaghahambing ang mga kabihasan sa Asya (Sumer, Indus, at Shang).	2
Napahahalagahan ang mga bagay at kaisipang Asyano pinagbatayan (sinocentrism, divine origin, devaraja, men of prowess, mandate of heaven, son of heaven).	3

The data imply that the 3 most difficult competencies for Araling Panlipunan 7 are as follows: Rank 1 Nasusuri ang mga kalagayang legal at tradisyon ng mga kababaihan sa iba't ibang uri ng pamumuhay. Rank 2. Nabibigyang kahulugan ang konsepto ng kabihasan at sibilisasyon at nailalahad ang mga katangian nito. Napaghahambing ang mga kabihasan sa Asya (Sumer, Indus, at Zhang). Rank 3 Napahahalagahan ang mga bagay at kaisipang Asyano pinagbatayan (sinocentrism, divine origin, devaraja, men of prowess, mandate of heaven, son of heaven). These competencies serve as the basis for developing the Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials.

Developed Material in Araling Panlipunan 7 based on the Three Least Mastered Competencies

The material that could be developed was Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials with Kotobee Apps downloaded from the Play Store, the most recent e-book reading software accessible on the Software Store. Learners will be able to easily read interactive e-books on their smartphones, PCs, and laptops. Kotobee Reader opens an e-book created with Kotobee Author. An e-book reading app that allows

you to browse books distributed by Kotobees' free shared library, download e-books distributed by other users, and read them offline. One of Koto bee's most impressive characteristics is its ability to interact with text. This program is truly optimized for executing interactive elements made by Kotobee authors. It ensures uniformity and fluidity throughout the web, desktop, iPad, iPhone, and Android devices. It is also responsive, adjusting to changing screen sizes and orientation adjustments.

Table 2. *Pretest Scores in Araling Panlipunan 7*

<i>Scores</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26-30	0	0%
21-25	84	27%
16-20	190	61%
11-15	37	12%
6-10	1	0%
0-5	0	0%
Total	312	100%

As the scores revealed from the data, it can be noted that during the pretest most of the students acquired a failing grade on their test which is defined as a low mastery level since the competencies have not been taught by the teacher and the mobile-assisted have not been used.

Table 3. *Pretest Scores in Araling Panlipunan 7*

<i>Scores</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
26-30	93	30%
21-25	213	68%
16-20	6	2%
11-15	0	0%
6-10	0	0%
0-5	0	0%
Total	312	100%

As the scores revealed from the data, it can be perceived that teaching using mobile-assisted learning materials has a better impact on student performance as most of the students have passed their test. It can be inferred that there is an increase in their scores after they are exposed to the developed material which is the mobile-assisted learning materials.

Significant difference between the pre and post-test scores in the competency Assessment in Araling Panlipunan 7

Table 4. *Test of Significant Difference between the Pre- and Post-test Scores*

<i>Test Scores</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>p Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Pre-Test	18.98	0.00	Reject Ho	Significant
Post-Test	24.25			

As seen in Table 4, since the computed p value of 0.00 is less than the 5% level of significance the null hypothesis is not proven. Therefore, there is significant difference between the pre- and post-test scores of students in the competency assessment in Araling Panlipunan.

The data implies that there is visible evidence to indicate a distinction between the obtained scores of the students in the pretest and posttest. Therefore, it can be noted that teaching using mobile-assisted learning materials has a favorable impact on the student's performance as compared to teaching using traditional instruction.

Enhancements that may be considered in the Developed Mobile-Assisted Learning Materials

Based on the results of test scores in the competency assessment enhancements that may be considered are as follows: (a). Provide more engaging activities that will unleash the potential of the learners to think critically. (b). Maximize the use of different features of the Kotobee reader not only putting videos and text on the material. (c). Include activities that may integrate with student's previous experiences.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following are the conclusions drawn from the results of the study.

There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest mean scores in Araling Panlipunan 7 based on the competency assessment. As a result, students performed better when taught using mobile-assisted learning materials.

The Mobile-Assisted Learning material presented is a great tool in honing, engaging, motivating, and encouraging active participation of the younger generation of learners to practice self-learning.

The developed mobile-assisted learning material made it manageable for students to grasp the competency in Araling Panlipunan 7.

Students in the twenty-first century may absorb lessons in a variety of learning styles, especially when teachers incorporate technology aids.

The use of technology by a teacher through organized and skilled planning with various platforms allows students to become more motivated and active participants in the learning environment.

The developed Mobile-Assisted Learning Material for Araling Panlipunan has been proven to be a conducive tool where a new approach to the teaching-learning process could have brought a progression in studies as learners would show their eagerness to explore the modernized world of education in which most of their interest is situated.

It is also good to note that the mobile-assisted learning materials utilize the Kotobee app which may run both online and offline that solve the issue of the digital divide.

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